

101112135 - IDERHA

Integration of heterogeneous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory and HTA Acceptance

WP1 – Infrastructure and tools for integration of data

D1.1 Data and analysis platform architecture (incl. different data sources and data types support) (1)

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Executive Summary

The present document, entitled “Data and analysis platform architecture (incl. different data sources and data types support) (1)”, provides an overview of the technical infrastructure designed for the IDERHA project. It is delivered as the first public version of the platform’s architecture under Deliverable (D)1.1, due at Month (M)12, and was developed under the coordination of the UNILU team, based on extensive discussions conducted among the consortium partners within Work Package (WP)1 and beyond.

The IDERHA architecture is being designed to address the challenges of federated access and analysis of health data to support better exchange of electronic health data for research, innovation, but also for policy-making and regulatory purposes [1]. The IDERHA project’s first year was spent defining the initial requirements, setting up or selecting the basic standards to follow, investigating the current landscape, and discussing the approaches and solutions among the project partners. This led to defining the necessary components, node layout and standards. Implementing of small-scale technical proofs of concept (PoCs) allowed for further refining of the plans. The project aligns with major communities and initiatives like GA4GH, ELIXIR, IDS, EHDS, Gaia-X and DSSC (Data Spaces Support Centre), contributing to the development of existing standards and service implementations.

The design of the architecture is driven by the principles of EU data spaces (by DSSC), data sovereignty and security, interoperability, and FAIRness. The approach is robust to changing requirements and plans, as it deploys many small, specialized services instead of a monolithic platform. This allows for easy replacement of components if needed and enables interoperability through the use of known standards.

The architecture has been frequently discussed in diverse contexts, and the approach has been able to address most needs with minor adjustments. Plans for the second year include developing a PoC by M18 to prove the technical feasibility of the architecture, identifying further requirements, and aligning with other initiatives and terminologies. The members of the development team will continue to engage in discussions within the consortium and with data providers to improve understanding of their requirements and make necessary technical adjustments. Further refinements of the architecture are anticipated by M24, driven by the PoC in M18 and detailed consortium findings.

The document concludes that there has been no deviation from the anticipated scope of delivery.

Introduction

The IDERHA project (Integration of heterogenous Data and Evidence towards Regulatory & HTA Acceptance) [2] aims to enhance innovation within the EU health care system by developing one of the first pan-European health data spaces [3]. The solution – hereafter called the IDERHA platform – is set to overcome the obstacles that currently hinder appropriate access to, sharing of, use and reuse of digital health care and patient data. This will be achieved by creating technical solutions that allow secure sharing and analysis of data in a federated setting, i.e., with analysis code moving to the data, instead of data moving for the analysis. The value of the IDERHA platform will be demonstrated through a set of use cases in the context of Lung Cancer (LC) disease. Nonetheless, the technical components developed as parts of the IDERHA data space will remain generic and disease-agnostic.

In this report (D1.1 in M12) we describe the architecture of the IDERHA platform, focusing on data access and data analysis aspects. In the subsequent parts of the Introduction, we summarise our architecture design approach and principles we followed. We mention the characteristics of the data, including data types and data sources, as well as analysis types. In the Methods section, we describe the relevant major steps performed to develop the architecture. In the Results section, we discuss the details of the designed architecture by describing the components of the IDERHA platform, their roles and interconnections, as well as the standards and principles they support. Specifically, we focus here on the alignment with the Trusted Research Environment (TRE) best practices [4]. Finally, the Discussion section presents the open questions and design issues that have not been included in this version of the architecture, and that need to be further elaborated as the project progresses.

This document deliberately does not disclose technical details of the infrastructure under development until they have more matured. Corresponding technical diagrams and workflow designs are shared and discussed internally with project partners; relevant details will be described in project's Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Protection Impact Assessment (DPIA) documents.

The design of the IDERHA architecture will continue to evolve during the upcoming months of the project, alongside the progress of the technical implementations by the partners and the identification of additional needs and requirements. The initial implementation of this architecture will be developed, deployed, tested, and demonstrated to work, before finally being delivered as a proof of concept (PoC) in D1.2 at M18. Further details of the architecture will be added and/or adjusted to ensure the design satisfies the functional and non-functional requirements and follows all relevant standards, regulations and best practises, such as related to security features, European and partners' national regulations, data providers' policies, etc. An updated version of the platform architecture will be published as D1.3 at M24

Approach

Building a dataspace, especially in a health data context, produces a wide variety of challenges. While there exist platforms that address some of these challenges, there is no single integrated solution to cover all needs. Such a solution would somehow have to be flexible and extendable enough to address project specific needs, while also solve common use-cases. These common use-cases are being defined in various ongoing initiatives, such as EHDS [3] and TEHDAS [5]. In designing the IDERHA platform, we plan to cover those, as well as to align with existing standards, good practice guidelines and emerging strategic initiatives and regulations, primarily in the European health data domain, such as GDPR, DGA, Data Act, etc. Thus, a broad sense interoperability is a guiding principle for the infrastructure design.

Realizing this, we approach the problem from a perspective that allows us to easily leverage and re-use existing building blocks (tools, frameworks, standards) and – if needed – develop the missing functionalities and connections. The resulting infrastructure will be thus modular, flexible and extensible, built of

independent but standardised components that can be replaced or supplemented with additional elements to evolve according to new needs, regulations or external developments.

- **Privacy- and Security-by-design**

Privacy and Security are key factors that drive our architectural design choices. Rather than addressing these factors separately from the business use-case (distribution of algorithms), they are part of this use-case itself. This causes a significant shift in the way we think about platform design. Where before, one might consider the distribution of algorithms the primary use-case, and add security and privacy elements afterwards, we take a step back and ask the question on how we can technically transfer a research question from one place into another, and receive a response, without violating privacy and security requirements. This way of thinking is technically reflected in the way that the entire access control layer is inverted, with data providers remaining in full control of the data access and processing, while the central components of the platform being only responsible for orchestration and brokering of the existing, approved access grants and analyses. Data processing outputs are privacy preserving in nature by expert/independent certification of algorithms that produce them. the platform follows privacy-by-design principles.

- **FAIR**

The architecture is being devised with the assumption of building a FAIR [6] infrastructure (FAIR-based services, workflows, processes, etc.) and supporting FAIR data in mind.

- **Findability:** One of the basic IDERHA goals is to support discoverability of data resources through user-facing components such as: data catalog, algorithm catalog and data linking services, based on rich metadata description of the resources. In the backend, internal components (EDC, DRS, TRS, monitoring services – see details in Results sec. 1.1) will be responsible for cataloguing all resources used and produced by the platform.
- **Accessibility:** Supporting accessibility of the resources, according to the principles of transparency, data security and sovereignty, will be ensured with state-of-the-art authentication and authorisation mechanisms, based on flexible yet standardised data access policies and processes, implemented through internal IDERHA components (e.g., identity and visa brokering mechanisms, EDC).
- **Interoperability:** Interoperability is one of the key pillars for building the IDERHA platform to ensure its flexibility and connectivity with external tooling and platforms (or other data spaces). Thus, the platform will be compliant with established standards (for a detailed yet non-exhaustive list of applied standards, see Results sec. 1.1) at multiple levels:
 - Interoperability of software: by supporting known technical industry standards (e.g., OIDC), international standards (e.g., eIDAS), community standards (e.g., GA4GH standards, LS ID), or open software standards (e.g., CWL),
 - Interoperability of tools: by integrating existing tools and frameworks (FML platforms such as NVIDIA FLARE, Flower),
 - Interoperability of data: by providing tools supporting widely recognised data description and modelling standards (e.g., DATS, OMOP CDM, HL7 FHIR, DICOM),
 - Interoperability of legal and data governance frameworks: by implementing solutions that support European/international regulations (e.g. GDPR),
- **Reusability:** The platform will support quality and reproducible research by ensuring workflow reproducibility (via data versioning and containerisation mechanisms, supported by DRS, TRS and monitoring components). A second aspect to reproducibility materializes through the contribution to open-source implementations of known standards, which will allow others to investigate and re-use parts of the IDERHA platform.

- **DSSC principles**

In addition, IDERHA platform will adhere to the following DSSC principles [7]:

- Clear governance framework,
- Enabling data transactions implying trustworthiness of the data transaction, emphasising qualities of the infrastructure for data sharing such as efficiency, security, control, transparency, quality, scalability, and regulatory compliance,
- Enabling trust amongst the participants,
- Enabling data sovereignty (i.e., the capability of individual or organisations to control the data and exercise their rights on the data they have).

Data sources and data types

The IDERHA platform will be a federated solution that allows discovery, access and analysis of data from connected resources, hosted by different Data Providers in databases on their own premises. The Data Providers remain sovereign data holders, who stay in full control of the data offered to the users via the platform, and remain responsible for ensuring data quality and standardisation, data pseudonymisation, data access request process, approval of the algorithms to be offered by IDERHA for their data, validation of the data access before running the analysis and (potentially) approval of the analysis results before releasing them from the premises (so-called “airlock” mechanism).

The technical solution developed as the infrastructure underlying the IDERHA platform will be generally disease/indication as well as data type agnostic. However, for the demonstration of value, the data analysis health data in Use Cases related to LC patient journey will be tackled. Dedicated algorithms will be developed (by WP2) based on the health records of LC patients that will be delivered to IDERHA by the Data Providers following the required data description standards and quality standards (recommended by WP4). As currently planned within the IDERHA project to address the planned Use Cases, patients’ clinical data will be primarily delivered as OMOP CDM [8], and imaging data in DICOM format [9]. Additional data formats, like NifTI [10], according to the project’s needs and data availability, can be also handled, and custom algorithms and auxiliary tools, such as data format converters, may be provided/developed in the future.

Data analysis

Data analysis in IDERHA will be performed in a federated way, where the algorithms will be delivered to the data at Data Providers’ sites.

In general, before any other details are addressed, the question of centralized analysis approach vs. decentralized analysis approach in a federated setting must be discussed. In IDERHA a centralised federated analysis approach will be applied. In terms of the execution of data analysis flow, this implies the following major steps:

1. algorithms are distributed across a set of nodes (with a node meaning the location where the data and computational resources are available) where the local data processing takes place,
2. only derived data (aggregated results or ML model updates) are being returned to the central node for the cross-node aggregation (while still being handled with utmost care and in compliance with relevant governing frameworks),
3. researchers eventually receive and use the aggregated results (computed by the central node).

An alternative scenario, i.e., fully decentralised federated analysis would rely on the federated data nodes communicating directly with each other without the coordination via the central node. The reasons behind the decision on a centralised and not a fully decentralized approach (e.g. implementable via blockchain technology) are the following:

- Scalability concerns due to the number of legal agreements needed for N (many) nodes connecting to N (many) other nodes versus the current 1 (one) to N (many) approach.
- Unavailability of adequate algorithms — With the exception of one solution (Swarm Learning Framework, [11]), none of the investigated open ML frameworks (e.g. NVIDIA FLARE [12], Flower [13]) supported a fully decentralized approach.
- System complexity — The increased technical challenge of maintaining a network with no definite place for storing models, aggregating results, or orchestrating multi-node tasks (e.g. discovery and monitoring).

The main focus of the core IDERHA infrastructure is to enable federated exploratory data analysis and federated machine learning (FML) to the researchers. IDERHA platform will support the latter by employing existing FML frameworks, that will be integrated within the data space with other components, such as the ones responsible for user and data access management. While the infrastructure is being designed based on the principle of interoperability and should be generic enough to support different FML solutions in the future, the first focus will be on one centralised FML framework of choice: NVIDIA FLARE [12], which has been selected (by WP2) for development of the first algorithms for the IDERHA Use Cases.

Methods

The development of the architecture was conducted as a collaborative task across the members of WP1, supported by other IDERHA WPs, and involved:

- Identification of basic requirements and steps needed to design the architecture via discussion with project members at the stages of the proposal preparation, the project setup and the IDERHA Kick-Off Meeting (Berlin, 18-19.04.2023) and during the project development.
- Extensive landscape analysis, involving identification and analysis of existing solutions and building blocks for federated data management and analysis, as well as the alignment with other existing and upcoming projects and initiatives (especially EHDS2, TEHDAS, EOSC ENTRUST and TITAN).
- Applying agile project management approach (based on defined initiatives, epics, and user stories) across WP1, managed and documented via WP1's workbench in Notion software, and partners' project management tools.
- Regular discussions during WP1 technical bi-weekly meetings, where the progress and issues related to individual user stories are handled.
- Regular reporting during WP1 monthly meetings, where the progress related to individual Tasks is presented to the WP1 members and representatives of other WPs present.
- Organisation of a WP1 Hackathon (Luxembourg, 20-21.07.2023), where the design of the IDERHA infrastructure was drafted and prototyped by WP1 members (UNILU, ISST).
- Refining the architecture during multiple working meetings between WP1 partners (mainly UNILU, ISST and Hygiaso).
- Discussing and setting up a Data Security Taskforce group to coordinate technical security specifications for IDERHA,
- Discussing and collecting requirements from data providers regarding the technical and legal requirements and possibilities for setting up federated nodes at Data Providers' premises.
- Close collaboration with the Data Management Plan (DMP) working group regarding technical, legal, security and analysis requirements (as collected from all relevant project partners) to be supported by the platform.

The progress of the work on the architecture was regularly released and communicated to the consortium members throughout the project:

- Three internal releases of the architecture during the first year of the project, accompanied with presentations and discussions on the design during WP1 monthly meetings (with WP1 partners and representatives of other WPs).
- Dissemination of the *Architecture release notes* to the project partners via a IDERHA mailing list.
- Presentations of the architecture and discussion during dedicated cross-WP meetings and exchange with:
 - o other WPs, mainly: WP2, WP3, WP4, WP5,
 - o Working Groups (WGs), such as Data Access Taskforce (DATF), DMP WG, DPIA WG, EHDS Alignment group,
 - o project members, e.g., during cross-WP Dataflow Requirements and Conditions workshop (11.09.2023, online), and during IDERHA extended SCOM F2F meeting (Sevilla, 06-07.11.2023),
 - o collaborators and experts in other European projects (ELIXIR, IMI EPND, YODA, AINed, etc.).
- Providing the information on the architecture, data processing and workflows to the Data Management Plan (DMP) and Data Protection and Impact Assessment (DPIA) documents, which were developed collaboratively and revised by the project partners before their releases.

Results

1 Standards and Services

In this section we describe the standards that we intend to use in IDERHA. Each standard addresses a specific issue; all combined provide the backbone for the IDERHA infrastructure as a federated **Trusted Research Environment** [4], as described in sections 1.2 [Description of Nodes](#) and 1.4 [Trusted Research Environment Alignment](#) of the Results in this document below.

1.1 Cloud Computing

The Global Alliance for Genomics and Health (GA4GH) [15] has been working on developing various cloud API standards to “get the algorithm to the data” as part of their mission. These standards have been picked up by the European ELIXIR Compatible Cloud Analysis Platform initiative [16], which has produced their multiple implementations over the last few years. In the following, we describe the purpose of each of these standards in IDERHA, and the reasons why a few different implementations of each may be found in our network.

GA4GH TES (Task Execution Service)

A standard for describing and executing tasks by connecting to the underlying compute backend. This standard solves a major challenge in federated computation, related to the fact that each federated node may use a different cloud vendor or compute backend (e.g., Azure, AWS, or an own Kubernetes cluster). The first step to build a federated system is to unify these resources under a common API standard for task execution. For that reason, we anticipate using several implementations of this standard, each specific to a certain High Performance Computing (HPC) or cloud vendor API at the Data Providers.

TES Gateway

This is not a GA4GH standard, but it solves an important limitation when it comes to coordination between multiple TES services. Without a gateway, the routing of the tasks is up to the client who submits the tasks (usually via some client software). A gateway can be used to delegate this burden through a predefined logic, which can be arbitrary (like network distance) or, in our case, lead the request to the correct compute environment where the requested dataset resides and computational/HPC resources are available.

GA4GH WES (Workflow Execution Service)

A standard that supplements TES and vice-versa. Where a TES executes a task in one step, a WES allows to set tasks into relationship with each other via known workflow definition languages such as Snakemake or Common Workflow Language (CWL). This helps to structure complex tasks into smaller chunks of work, and thus to monitor and troubleshoot a long-running workflow. In a federated infrastructure this takes on an additional dimension via location, if we think of running tasks in multiple federated nodes in parallel and want to aggregate the results in one place.

GA4GH TRS (Tool Registry Service)

A standard that abstracts algorithmic resources, such as the tasks run by a TES or workflows orchestrated by a WES. An example for the implementation of a TRS can be a Docker Image Registry, or CWL workflow files stored and annotated in a database. This service ultimately defines what can be run on the IDERHA infrastructure.

GA4GH DRS (Dataset Registry Service)

A standard that abstracts and catalogues the actual storage situation of the data resources. Similar to a DNS service, it maps a resource id to a URL where the resource may be found. This enables components within the federated setup, such as a central meta catalogue, to refer to datasets via their ID (a stable identifier), while the underlying storage solution may change over time.

A DRS may also be used to catalogue other resources, such as workflow input parameter files or the results of analyses. The former is particularly important, as registering input parameters is an important step in making workflows reproducible. This functionality strongly synergizes with a TRS, which would be responsible for cataloguing the actual workflows.

DCAT Standard

Data CATalog (DCAT) is a Resource Description Framework (RDF) vocabulary that provides a standardized model to describe datasets and services that are published in data catalogues. Thereby, the DCAT standard facilitates interoperability, efficient sharing and consumption of metadata within and across catalogues by ensuring consistency in its representation. Thus, DCAT simplifies the discovery, exchange, and integration of datasets across the web, facilitating adherence to the FAIR Principles.

In IDERHA, the primary objective is enabling discoverability and use of the federated data resources. To this end, it is crucial to identify (metadata) requirements with respect to federated data sharing which pertains to the design and declarative development of the network's metadata catalogue. Such relevant metadata attributes to be identified may include titles, descriptions, keywords, data types, data modalities, data use conditions, access requirements, contact information, et cetera. In this context, DCAT enables to standardize metadata schemata to support and maintain consistency and completeness of metadata assets published by means of IDERHA's catalogue component in the data space. Moreover, DCAT is a beneficial standard to cross-reference datasets enhancing data discoverability, while considering the scalability and sustainability of the data space.

1.2 Security

OIDC (OpenID Connect)

OIDC is an increasingly popular standard built upon OAuth2 that enables user authentication and authorization, as well as Single-Sign-On (SSO) and the ability to add Multi-Factor Authentication (MFA) methods. It is widely supported by identity providers. It involves issuing of ID tokens, which may carry person specific information, as well as signed access grants. In our setup, we intend to follow the OIDC standard through the use Keycloak, a well-known open-source Identify and Access Management solution. Keycloak is also highly extendable, which will support the integration of other standards, like GA4GH passports.

eIDAS & eID

The EU Regulation on “electronic identification and trust services for electronic transactions in the internal market” [17] came into effect in 2014. It enables people and businesses to use their national electronic identification schemes in digital communication and transactions across the EU in interactions with authorities and administration and other businesses. Their digitally signed documents and transactions are equivalent to being executed on paper, thereby offering efficiency gains in the market. All member states mutually recognise each other's identity and signature credentials, which are secured by a set of national Trust Service Providers (TSP), qualified and certified against the eIDAS standard. The validity of any document or transaction signature or ID can be verified online anytime. In IDERHA we will use eIDs and/or digital identity certificates from TSPs to authenticate citizen users. An amendment of the eIDAS Regulation (eIDAS 2.0), approved by the EU Parliament Feb 29, 2024, will provide citizens and legal entities with European Digital Identity Wallets to participate in digital society and to access online public and private services.

In some non-EU countries corresponding regulations have been passed which are almost identical and technically interoperable, yet legally not mutually accepted (e.g. ZertS in Switzerland).

IDS (International Data Spaces) Standard — EDC (Eclipse Dataspace Components)

The International Data Space (IDS) standard has been defined by the International Data Spaces Association (IDSA) [18]. The IDS aims to create a secure and trusted data space (data infrastructure) where companies can exchange and link trusted data. It promotes collaboration and data-driven value by building a decentralized and interoperable ecosystem among participating actors. The goal of the IDSA is to establish the IDS as a globally recognized standard for sovereign data exchange. As part of the IDS initiative, the Eclipse Dataspace Components (EDC) provides a comprehensive technical framework that offers concepts, architecture, code, and examples for the standardized implementation of data spaces in all domains. It specifies a basic set of functions that can be reused and customized by data space initiatives. The EDC Connector is the central technical component of this framework, providing all the necessary functions for rule-based, secure, and cross-organizational data exchange. The Data Provider and Data Consumer are the key actors in these sovereign data transfers, connected through their respective EDC Connectors. Using their connector, the Data Provider defines a data contract (e.g., in Open Digital Rights Language [19]) by linking the dataset and specifying machine-readable policies (Data Access / Usage Control Conditions). The Data Consumer can negotiate the contract with the Data Provider by means of proposing a counteroffer or directly accept the initial terms. In the case of contract agreement, a sovereign (i.e., rule-based), technically secured, and cross-organizational data exchange occurs based on the pre-defined policies. These policies can be tailored to each use case, while considering applicable constraints and requirements. Emphasizing the above, the policies instantiate data access and usage conditions by representing their machine-readable (and typically standardized) version.

In IDERHA, a repository of standardized access / usage policies will be supplied for clinical Data Providers to select and specify for their datasets made available in the network.

GA4GH Passports

A GA4GH “passport” [20] is an aggregation of GA4GH “visas”. A GA4GH visa is a piece of signed information with a source, a target audience, and an expiration date, that can be used by a resource holder to announce whether a user has access to a certain resource. In our case, this will be Data Providers who can issue an access visa for the user. Visas, collected into a passport by the central visa broker, can then be passed around any service that requires the issued information for granting access to sensitive resources. Such services, called GA4GH “clearing houses”, make sure that the visa is authentic, valid, and relevant to make a technical decision about the access grant based on the submitted payload. Details regarding the payload can be found in the description of the IDS EDC, which is one of IDERHA’s most important clearing houses.

2 Description of Nodes

While the previous section was concerned with describing major standards to be used within the IDERHA platform, this section outlines how these standards are grouped together within so-called nodes. Nodes represent different physical locations that are planned, namely: a central node, many federated nodes and their compute environments, as well as their internal data management environments. (s. Figure 1)

Figure 1: IDERHA platform nodes and their relationships. Each node contains a set of components compliant with standards (depicted as hexagons, with their colours corresponding to a type of standards supported; see the Legend) that we plan to use to address project specific challenges.

2.1 Central Node

a. Description

The central node acts as the single point of entry for researchers to the IDERHA data space and as an orchestrator of tasks across all nodes. It provides user-facing services like a meta-catalogue for data and tools discovery, means to authenticate users, and to submit and monitor data access requests and federated analysis workflows, as well as a back end consisting of several services to enable these functionalities. The central node does not hold any data resources and, by design, cannot exercise control over federated nodes (as also described in Security). It is a place for discovery, request routing, and monitoring.

b. Technical Details

The discovery aspect is addressed via a central meta-catalogue of datasets and workflows. The proper description of the datasets (i.e., data resources handled at and offered by federated nodes for specific analyses) and the workflows (i.e., the algorithm/analyses resources that can be run within the IDERHA environment) is provided to enable the users to thoroughly understand, select and request the suitable resources for their needs.

The metadata standard that is planned to use for cataloguing the datasets is DCAT. Metadata are collected and updated automatically from the EDCs of all participating federated nodes via remote TES services, upon a request from the central catalogue.

Workflows, listed in the meta-catalogue UI for discovery of the available analysis types, are catalogued and handled through the TRS service at the central node. Their input parameters (and other non-personal data that may be associated with executing a workflow) will be catalogued in the DRS service for the purpose of ensuring and documenting the reproducibility of the workflow execution process.

Orchestration of workflows' execution, involving the operations of the necessary splitting, assigning and distributing of sub-tasks, is the responsibility of the WES service. While support for various workflow languages by WES is possible, we decided to focus our initial efforts on CWL, as a widely accepted and supported standard.

The execution of tasks at individual nodes is managed by TES services. The major responsibility of the TES in the central node is to orchestrate the aggregation of derived data and model updates. Unlike TES services at the federated nodes, the TES at the central node does not process nor engage with any source level data.

Finally, the central node acts as a user identity and data access visa broker to facilitate authentication and authorization processes at the federated nodes. We have currently no plans of managing identities within IDERHA but to intermediate between identity providers like LifeScience RI [21], which make use of the eduGAIN network [22], or trusted eIDAS [23] eID providers.

2.2 Federated Node

a. Description

A federated node in the IDERHA setup is usually the DMZ (demilitarized zone, i.e., separated, external part of the network) of a participating data provider (e.g., a hospital) or a similar compute environment at an associated cloud provider. Its primary purpose is the establishment of a technically supported data governance layer that controls the conditions under which algorithms may be applied to the (pseudonymized) data it holds, according to data provider's specification.

b. Technical Details

The EDC service in each federated node is one of the most important data governance components in the IDERHA setup. It enforces data access policies defined by the data provider and is the only service in the IDERHA stack that has direct access to the source databases. It uses the payloads of signed GA4GH access grant visas to temporarily release a subset of data into the compute environment of the DMZ.

In the compute environment of the federated node, we find data analysis frameworks, including ML frameworks, such as NVIDIA Flare, which run algorithms on the data subset released by EDC. Analysis outputs, i.e., derived results or established model parameters, are delivered back to the central node, and from there to the researcher. This transfer of derived results from the federated node to the central node is further described in [Security](#) and [Trusted Research Environment Alignment](#).

2.3 External HPC Node

a. Description

The separate compute node is an entirely optional concept and depends on the availability of HPC hardware in the federated node. A data provider may seek out a cloud provider if their local computing power is not sufficient for IDERHA's analysis requirements.

b. Technical Details

Computationally expensive components, such as NVIDIA Flare, may be moved from the federated node (DMZ) into the cloud provider solution. Architecturally, this will require some additional settings, mainly with regards to efficient and secure data transfer, which is why components like EDC and TES may also be needed there.

2.4 Data Provider

a. Description

The internal environment of a Data Provider will not contain any technical IDERHA components. It is responsible for Data Provider's specific processing such as handling data collection or data pseudonymization, prior to delivering data to the data provider's Federated Node and (optionally) their External HPC node (following data standards defined by WP4), as well as for the internal part of the datasets access request processes.

b. Technical Details

While this part of the infrastructure may not contain any technical components of IDERHA, a set of assumptions and requirements regarding local processes and data standards must be fulfilled by the Data Providers willing to join IDERHA as a Federated Node. Many of these requirements will be defined in detail by other IDERHA work packages (e.g., D4.2: Data standards Manual, or D4.5: Data Quality Framework) and thus we won't go into much detail in this document. What can be assumed however, is that it contains processes for dataset request access, processes for pseudonymization of data (prior to transfer into the DMZ), and that certain data standards (such as OMOP or DICOM) are followed.

2.5 Citizen Service Node

a. Description

This node provides the backend services to the citizens who access or consent to processing of their health data held on the smartphone app or with a data holder, such as passing citizen data requests to data holders at Federated Nodes or receiving their personal data from them through the IDERHA workflow. The Citizen

Service Node acts like a messenger service handling the communication flow between data requestors and data holders with inclusion of the citizen user where needed.

A core element is also handling the citizen user authentication (making sure the user is indeed the natural person they claim to be) and access, making sure only that person can access the data concerned. This is essential also in digital legally viable consenting as the data holder must be sure who has given their consent.

Figure 2: Identifying and authenticating the users on the platform is essential to ensure that consents can be relied upon and data is authorised to and received by the correct person.

b. Technical Details

Data users will be required to authenticate as members of their organisation (such as staff of a given hospital or research organisation). Single Sign-On will be offered for qualified organisations such as IDERHA partners since this organisation is accepted as trust provider via OIDC. We will also offer SSI [24] credentials via OIDC for which eIDAS or ZertS (Switzerland) qualified organisations serve as trust providers to authenticate natural persons in their private capacity (citizen). For certain use cases, we use WebAuthN standard, e.g., to extend access to a browser session, authenticated in presence by the interacting individual(s).

Such legally reliable authentication methods will be used to authenticate and therefore render digital consents robust for the relying party. Note, that a staff member of an organisation may use the application in their professional capacity or with a different ID as a private individual.

2.6 Citizen App

a. Description

A citizen's personal data will be held on their personal device (iOS or Android smartphone) or controlled from it in their personal private (cloud) storage via the Citizen App. Therefore, such data is held fully de-centrally, i.e., there is no aggregation of personal data from many subjects in any central database.

The Citizen Service Node transmits encrypted data or references to it but does and cannot access it. This also holds for data requests and consents. Personal data requests, including also consent requests, are relayed in a privacy preserving way to the citizens, who accept or decline these autonomously in the Citizen App. This satisfies the GDPR Art. 9a requirement for explicit consent (or opt-out). Upon acceptance of data requests, respective citizen data is made available in a temporary and personal cloud storage resource and the access link shared back with the requester for them to download their data. This mechanism therefore supports the envisaged EHDS Access Service and opt-out mechanism.

b. Technical Details

Personal data held on the smartphone of citizen is access controlled by the device access controls as the user has configured them (PIN, FaceID, TouchID). Digital Personal ID certificates issued by qualified Trust Service Providers (which are nationally regulated under eIDAS or ZertS) serve as credentials, which can be used to authenticate the user on their smartphone when necessary to make use of a service offered by the Citizen Service Node. Such services will include accepting or submitting data requests, where they will be prompted to present their digital ID credentials. Citizens therefore do not require an account registration to use the smartphone application. Consequentially, the Citizen Service Node does not know the identity of the Citizen users (Privacy by Design).

3 Security

In the following sections we will describe some notable elements of our security design. In addition to the regular efforts of WP1, two dedicated work groups have been set up within the project to address platform's security and integrity from legal and technical perspectives (Data Security Taskforce and Data Access Taskforce, respectively). These taskforces are also responsible for deciding on formal regular external auditing procedures and necessary certifications.

3.1 Core Services Security Concept

Security is a legally and technically complex topic in any federated network because of the high degree of autonomy of each participating node and the potential sensitivity of the data that reside in each site. The proposed technical design must ensure that data providers stay in control (keyword: zero trust) and that all processes are fully transparent and auditable. Furthermore, the potential impact of malicious actors must be reduced to a minimum. In the following we will describe various techniques that we intend to employ to satisfy these requirements, as well as discuss potential alternatives.

Authentication describes the process of establishing the entity behind an account ("who"), as opposed to authorization, which describes the activities this account is allowed to perform ("what"). In our design, neither will be provided by nor occur in the central node, because that would imply certain degree of trust or control, which ideally should not exist or at least be minimized to a few well-known limitations. This is why, instead, we only broker externally signed and verifiable information for identity and access. In addition, part of our objective is to define process-based structures, such as an Algorithm Approval Committee, which will be responsible for certifying algorithms according to their privacy preserving properties, for the use in the IDERHA platform.

While the exact choice of identity providers (and potential leveraging of initiatives such as LifeScience RI or eduGAIN, and the eIDAS solution via national eID systems) is still an ongoing discussion, the underlying technology has already been agreed. Through OpenID Connect (OIDC) we will obtain signed ID tokens for the user of such providers and broker them through the central node alongside any analysis or access requests to the federated nodes, where they may be verified for authenticity directly with the issuing provider. Potentially malicious access attempts with modified or self-issued ID tokens will not be able to pass this check. After the validation of the token, it is now up to the data provider to decide on whether they accept this information or initiate further identity verification processes before they authorise the access.

The result of a completed verification process could technically also be brokered, just like the initial ID token, to other data providers to help support their own decision-making processes. Whether or not this will find application in IDERHA is an ongoing discussion, but the technical standard that would enable such functionality does not only support brokering of verified identities, it also supports the sharing of data access decisions through so-called GA4GH "visas", which play a major role in the authorization layer.

Our goal is to open data silos by providing technical assurance for various aspects of data governance. Access must be limited to fields and records required for a specific research objective according to data minimisation principles. It will be also limited to the purpose that was consented to by data provider (i.e., concrete algorithms), to the categories of algorithms that have been agreed upon (s. new EU AI Act), and will be revocable and time limited. It also needs to be monitored, transparent and auditable.

In our setup, this will be the major responsibility of the EDC Connector implementation of the IDS standard. The job of this connector is to take in a request and release the specified data into the processing environment on-demand. It does so based on pre-defined policies (also referable to as access / usage policies). In essence, those EDC policies consist of sets of subjects (Data Consumers), objects (datasets), and action (algorithm) specifications which also reflect basic information provided by the GA4GH passport visas.

An EDC, according to GA4GH Passport terminology, is a so-called clearinghouse. This is where the previously mentioned visas become important again. An EDC needs certain information, such as the DAC decision, in order to release data. A visa is the verifiable technical representation of such a decision. It is issued and signed by the data provider and may contain a simple access decision, or complex access limitations, such as prohibiting certain types of algorithms (e.g., “No AI processing”) or limiting the fields that the researcher is allowed to access.

Once this visa is issued by the custodian, the broker at the central node is responsible for sharing this information as a passport (i.e., aggregation of visas) during a workflow execution, such that all service clearing-houses in any involved node in the workflow may independently audit and permit (by default, deny) the execution of any step of a workflow and the access to data. Authenticity of a visa is ensured by verifying its signature with the public certificate of the issuer at the data provider.

Security is further addressed in [Trusted Research Environment Alignment](#) section below, but it should be generally understood that we intend to employ best practices wherever possible, even if not explicitly mentioned, such as the use of HTTPS between services in different networks. We will describe the full security design in detail in future documents related to the IDERHA platform architecture, such as D1.3 (M24).

3.2 Citizen Services Security Concept

In the Citizen solution, personal health data is held fully de-centrally, i.e. at the level of an individual on their smartphone or on their personal private cloud. We therefore avoid a central large database which would pose a significant security exposure. All personal health data is encrypted when stored on device and in cloud, as well as when transmitted and keys and access to them are controlled from the smartphone (wallet).

The Citizen Service Node avoids having access to personal data and services are designed with this objective in mind. Using SSI credentials allows creating a password-less interaction for citizen and reusing login credentials of trusted organisations for transactions on behalf of that organisation (SSO).

The solution provider (HYG) is in the process of implementing Information Security, Cyber Security and Privacy standard ISO27001 and Medical Information Security ISO27799 to support trust of collaborating parties in IDERHA and beyond to provide data holders and users with assurance on any personal health data processing.

4 Trusted Research Environment Alignment

In this chapter we discuss TRE best practices and analyse how well IDERHA aligns with them. The following “5 Safe” assumptions for a TRE are described in details in the next subsections:

5 Safes	Short Definition / Summary
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Safe People	Only trained, authorised individuals can access the data
Safe Project	Use of data must be appropriate, which projects must justify
Safe Setting	Analysis platform actively minimizes the risk of unauthorised access, use or disclosure
Safe Data	Comprehensive metadata descriptions, minimization principles, and pseudonymization
Safe Output	Only non-disclosive output data is subject to release from a TRE

It is important to note that, while a good base to start with, TRE best practices do not always apply to each use-case, especially in a federated context, and are sometimes not feasible to achieve with reasonable effort. We describe such exceptions and, if applicable, alternative approaches used.

It should also be noted, that in the context of TRE alignment below, the term “data custodian” corresponds to the term “data provider” used elsewhere across the document.

4.1 Safe People

Definition: Ensuring that individuals accessing the IDERHA data space are trustworthy and have the necessary permissions to handle responsibly the datasets they want to access. This involves verifying identities, providing appropriate training on data handling procedures and ethical guidelines, and implementing access controls to limit access to authorized researchers. Below, it is elaborated to what extent the IDERHA data space complies with the best practices of Safe People.

No.	Best Practices (Centralized TRE)	Alignment
A1	Data Custodians should have processes to verify the identity of Individuals from the information they supply.	Yes – via ID tokens from trusted eIDAS service providers or via internal process of the Data Custodians.
A2	Data Custodians should have processes to verify the status of <i>Individuals</i> from information <i>they</i> or their <i>Organisations</i> provide regarding their Accredited / Approved / Bonafide analyst / researcher status or equivalent.	Yes – through IdPs like LifeScience RI and eduGAIN network or via internal process.
A3	Data Custodians should have processes to verify that <i>Individuals</i> undertake and renew Information Governance Training in support of their accreditation status.	Unclear – under discussion, potentially out of IDERHA scope.
A4	Data Custodians should maintain records of signed agreements by <i>Individuals and Organizations</i> documenting their legal undertakings governing their access to the data, including capturing declarations of funding/sponsorship, commercial interests and any potential conflicts of interest.	Yes ¹ - GA4GH visas represent technical access decision, but contract negotiation is handled directly by data custodians.
A5	TRE providers should be able to apply authorisation policies to enable access to services based on the access approved for each individual.	Yes – authorization policies are defined in EDC. Access is technically represented by GA4GH visas, which will be evaluated while accessing data according to those policies.
A6	TRE providers should maintain a record of all user access performed by <i>Individuals</i> for audit.	Yes – various services in the platform will record this information, centrally and in the federated node.
A7	Data Custodians should have processes to disbar users in breach of service with an appeal process.	Yes – user visas can be revoked by data custodians anytime.

No.	Best Practices (Federated TRE)	Alignment
FA1	TRE providers should implement OIDC and OAUTH2 APIs to link to identities provided through the Gateway.	Yes - IDERHA uses the OpenID Connect (OIDC) standard.
FA2	Data Custodians should define institutionally validated identities they will trust from the information they supply (A1).	Yes - identities are offered by external identity providers and data custodians form decision upon the data access request.

FA3	Data Custodians should define which external accreditation status attached to an individual's digital identity they will accept (A2).	Yes - acceptance of accreditation status is handled by each data custodian , according to the regulations in European law.
FA4	Data Custodians should define which external evidence of information governance training attached to an individual's digital identity they will accept (A3).	Possible – Currently being discussed in IDERHA consortium.
FA5	Data Custodians should collect as much information about individuals and organizations as possible, furthermore, documenting legal undertakings governing their access to the data. Additional information to be captured by data custodians includes declarations of funding/sponsorship, commercial interests and any potential conflicts of interest (A4).	Yes ¹
FA6	Data Custodians should ensure that any disbar process is flagged against an individual's identity, so it is visible across the ecosystem. They should also actively check for such flags attached to the identity of any individual accessing their TRE (A7).	Possible – information can be associated with personal identity through central broker, but whether this information is used at scale depends on EDC policies at each data custodian. Technically, we have the means to block access to the entire IDERHA network in severe cases.

4.2 Safe Projects

Definition: Ensuring that research projects conducted within the IDERHA data space are ethically sound, comply with legal and regulatory requirements, and have appropriate safeguards in place to protect data privacy and confidentiality. This includes conducting ethical reviews of research proposals, obtaining informed consent from participants when necessary, and implementing techniques to minimize data privacy and security risks. Below, it is elaborated to what extent the IDERHA data space complies with the best practices of Safe Projects.

No.	Best Practices (Centralized TRE)	Alignment
P1	<i>Individuals and organizations</i> should provide detailed project descriptions including project methodology, funder/sponsor information, ethics approvals and time period of access.	Yes ¹
P2	Data Custodians should provide detailed guidance of the data access request process, including time frames, requirements and decision-making process.	Yes – this part is envisioned as being included in the Metadata Catalog.
P3	Data Custodians should consider providing the ability for Individuals to submit and process basic enquiries of the data they hold prior to submission of a formal access request.	Yes ¹
P4	Data Custodians should provide a proportionate data access request form to collect all relevant information about the individual/organization's project.	Yes ¹
P5	Data Custodians should inform and update individuals on the status & processing times of their application and allow for individual appeals process.	Yes ¹
P6	Data Custodians data access decision making processes should have meaningful involvement of patient and public / lay representatives.	Yes ¹ - Usually handled through ethics committee.
P7	Data Custodians should maintain a public Data Use Register with the aspiration that it is updated in 'real time' with approved projects.	Yes ¹ - supported by means of EDC event logs and GA4GH Visa Issuer's logs.

No.	Best Practices (Federated TRE)	Alignment
FP1	Data Custodians should consider the HDR UK designed Five SAFE form as the baseline for collection of data for project approval, following [P4]; Data Custodians should provide a proportionate data access request form to collect all relevant information about the individual/organization's project.	Yes ¹

4.3 Safe Settings

Definition: Creating a secure and controlled environment for data access and analysis, which includes the implementation of technical components for encryption, access controls, and audit logging to prevent unauthorized access and data breaches. This also involves security measures to protect against unauthorized access to infrastructure components (i.e., the federated nodes) where data is stored and processed. Below, it is elaborated to what extent the IDERHA data space complies with the best practices of Safe Settings.

No.	Best Practices (Centralized TRE)	Alignment
S1	TRE providers should implement processes and systems that hold and manage data securely, encrypted at rest with data encryption keys exclusively controlled by Data Custodians.	Yes ¹ – Source databases are handled by data custodian and should be encrypted at rest.
S2	TRE providers should implement mechanisms to provision a minimized dataset bespoke to the individuals request encrypted with a separate key accessible by the project individuals.	Yes – Data is made accessible for analysis under data minimization principles but is not shared directly with the researcher. Researchers or care providers may also request health data from individual citizens with their consent and access it through encrypted storage. The citizen can request and have their own data shared encrypted by a data custodian.
S3	TRE providers should provide a secure environment to allow individuals to perform their analyses using tools supplied by the TRE provider and/or tools requested to be deployed by the individual.	Yes – approved algorithms are stored in the TRS and available for remote execution. New ones may be submitted and approved through manual review process.
S4	TRE providers should provide services that allow individuals to remotely execute analysis workflows using TRE supplied tools or research software with minimal hands-on access to the data.	Yes – Researchers do not access the plaintext data à algorithms-to-data concept.
S5	TRE Providers should publish their security design and implementation reports for review.	Yes – security design will be released later, alongside DPIA documents. This deliverable focuses on primary standards used.
S6	TRE providers should provide assurance statements that ensure their processes and systems are conformant to secure data processing standards – ISO 27001, IGTToolkit/DSPT, ONS/UKSA Accredited Processor	No – it is unclear for the moment which certifications are required by data custodians. We will revisit this point in the future.
S7	TRE providers should allow individuals to specify software, research code, reference data, configurations to be deployed with their SAFE Setting which may be subject to a review process before deployment.	Partially - Algorithm Review Committee approves all algorithms before they are published in the Meta-Algorithm Catalogue for common use. Currently there are no individual arrangements planned.
S8	TRE providers should make every attempt to support the ongoing collaboration between project members, including provide collaboration software – Git, Shared doc.	Partially – We do not consider collaborative workspaces at this stage in the project, although sharing/adding new user algorithms to IDERHA upon approval process will be possible. We also support collaboration through support channels, calls, and code repositories

No.	Best Practices (Federated TRE)	Alignment
FS1	TRE providers should provide ingress and egress (where allowed) to transfer data and code securely between SAFE Settings.	Yes – Traffic between components in different networks is encrypted. Traffic between components inside the same network is isolated through virtualization (Docker/Kubernetes) and can also be encrypted if needed.

		Algorithms (container images) are fetched from a strictly controlled non-public registry. Source database in federated node sits in a restricted subnet (only egress through EDC).
FS2	TRE providers should adopt common <i>pseudo identifier generation processes</i> to enable safe linkage between SAFE Settings.	Yes – we consider this criterion fulfilled because, while no common pseudo identifier generation process is planned, the data linking is, which is the goal of FS2.
FS3	TRE providers should provide services that allow individuals to remotely execute analysis workflows using TRE supplied tools or externally supplied research software.	Yes – Algorithms are deployed remotely through container images. <i>Algorithm Review Committee</i> approves new algorithms for inclusion in central Tool Registry Service (TRS) and common use.

4.4 Safe Data

Definition: Ensuring that the data used within the IDERHA data space are of sufficient quality, and their utilization is ethically and legally decent. This requires establishing appropriate data governance measures, conducting risk assessments, and implementing data management practices to maintain data integrity and confidentiality throughout the entire lifecycle. Below, it is elaborated to what extent the IDERHA data space complies with the best practices of Safe Data.

No.	Best Practices (Centralized TRE)	Alignment
D1	<i>Data Custodians</i> should provide descriptive, semantic and technical metadata about their datasets publicly available in human and machine-readable form.	Yes - Data custodians provide descriptive, semantic and technical metadata in human & machine-readable form using DCAT standard. The metadata is published in the IDERHA Metadata Catalogue.
D2	<i>Data Custodians</i> should provision data using a standardized format supporting well-known data standards.	Yes - Data Custodians follow the IDERHA project guidelines on data standards; for the UCs they are expected to provide data in OMOP-CDM 5.4 and image formats like DICOM and NIFTY.
D3	<i>Data custodians</i> should ensure all direct identifiers are removed from source data assets prior to onboarding into the TRE and provide a lay summary of how these processes are managed.	Yes - Data custodians only include pseudonymized or anonymised data into the IDERHA data space. Actual process details are subject to data custodians.
D4	<i>TRE provider</i> should provide mechanisms and process for researchers to request ingress of external (additional) data to be used by researchers as part of their research.	No – currently not in the scope of IDERHA, but technically easily achievable if a host for such data can be found and added as a federated node. This functionality will be revisited at a later stage in the project.
D5	<i>TRE Providers</i> should provide data linkage services to allow users to request linkage of datasets with data held internally or externally to the TRE provider.	Partially – This is part of the citizen service offering that needs to be supported by a data custodian.
D6	<i>TRE providers</i> should implement appropriate data minimization proportionate to sensitivity and the approved use of the data.	Yes – Data custodian will be given technical means to issue conditions and scope in which data may be accessed. This will be handled by EDC policies and GA4GH visas.
D7	<i>TRE providers</i> should be able to provision project specific workspaces that maintain the integrity of the provisioned data and ensure multi-tenant security and privacy.	Partially – Each researcher will work in their own virtually separated personal workspace(s) to handle results (derived data) and workflows, no multi-tenant projects workspaces are currently planned. Source data are not part of any workspace. They remain at the data custodian and are only released

		temporarily into the compute environment of the Data Custodian for specific workflows of individual researchers.
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No.	Best Practices (Federated TRE)	Alignment
FD1	TRE providers should consider progressively adopting a Common Data Model, agreed not only across the Alliance but across the wider TRE ecosystem and developing processes to generate transformations of data assets into this format	Yes – data custodians follow IDERHA project guidelines on data standards that requires OMOP and DICOM; data standardization processes are supported by WP4 but their implementation depends on data custodians.

4.5 Safe Outputs

Definition: Ensuring that the scientific outputs generated within the IDERHA data space are accurate, reliable, and appropriately validated. This prescribes to consider verifying the integrity of data and analysis results, conducting peer reviews of research findings, and providing transparency about the research process. Below, it is elaborated to what extent the IDERHA data space complies with the best practices of Safe Outputs.

No.	Best Practices (Centralized TRE)	Alignment
O1	Individuals should be able to apply for a data or code release from the safe setting.	Yes – source data is not released from federated node, but derived data may. Code of the algorithms offered by IDERHA, according to the IP, might be accessible.
O2	Data Custodians should implement timely processes and systems to assess and decide on the data release applications in a consistent manner, including decision provenance & appeals process.	Yes ¹ – Source data never leaves data custodians premise, but it is released into the data custodians compute environment in a controlled fashion through the EDC which enforces local policies.
O3	Data Custodians should provide open and clear documentation of the statistical disclosure control policies including the assessment criteria that are used to evaluate data export requests.	Yes ¹
O4	TRE Providers should provide software solutions to manage data export requests.	Yes – Source data does not leave data custodian, but results (derived data) are exported, as defined in the approved workflows. In the citizen service infrastructure, there exist mechanisms for the citizens to request and receive their own personal data (as per GDPR).
O5	TRE Airlock managers should aim to harmonize and coordinate output checking and data release management processes with other TRE Airlock managers and external expert groups.	No – It is currently still unclear if airlocks are needed as the approved algorithms are strictly controlled. If airlocks are needed, it is unlikely that various data custodians can be aligned on their release process, as this is out of scope for IDERHA.
O6	Data Custodians and Individuals should ensure appropriate training is afforded to staff and individuals to ensure individuals are able to produce outputs that require minimal effort to check.	Partially – algorithms are verified privacy preserving, so training should not be needed. Such training itself is out of scope for IDERHA.
O7	TRE Providers should consider providing a mechanism to stably archive datasets that support publications but cannot be exported with externally visible IDs and support reviewer access if requested.	Partially – algorithms and input parameters will be stored in a FAIR way to enable reproducibility, but support for dataset archiving is not currently planned. Needs further discussion.
O8	TRE Providers should provide a mechanism to archive an entire project workspace for a determined duration.	Yes – Workspace may be achieved, but remote source data will not be associated with the workspace per design. Derived

		data may be archived. Needs further discussion.
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No.	Best Practices (Federated TRE)	Alignment
FO1	TRE providers should consider deploying Beacons within their safe setting to support the programmatic generation of safe outputs from standardized external queries, subject to airlock review processes to approve acceptable query types.	Unclear – Discovery via Beacons is definitively nice to have but is currently not discussed. This may be added in a later project stage.

¹ The basic assumption in IDERHA is that these processes exist and are implemented correctly at each data custodian (usually a hospital) site. It is out of scope of this project to certify or enforce certain procedures in each federated node.

Discussion

In this document, due in M12 of the project, we summarise the assumptions and design decisions for the development of the IDERHA infrastructure. The implementation of the presented approach is in progress, and the next milestone is a proof of concept (PoC) implementation, due in M18. Before the PoC, the feasibility discussions remain mostly theoretical, however we can derive some observations from the many in-depths conversations across the IDERHA consortium.

In year 1, we have opted to define the node layout and the standards used within. This led to small-scale technical PoCs in which it was demonstrated that certain core components could be integrated. These discoveries helped us to understand the architectural gaps, which led to an inclusion of new standards. In parallel, we would frequently discuss our architecture in various contexts within the consortium, which provided us with important feedback and also led to an increasingly clearer understanding of requirements and how to address them technically.

By aligning ourselves with major communities like GA4GH, ELIXIR, and IDS we discovered various (microservice) standards developed and used there. Being part of these communities ourselves, we will be able to contribute to further development of existing standards and service implementations through the use cases that are driven by the IDERHA project requirements.

Our approach also provides a certain robustness to changing requirements and plans, as we are not building a monolithic platform, but instead deploy many small, specialized services, which can be easily replaced by other components if needed. And finally, the choice of using known standards is an important step to enable interoperability and allows for the development of reusable client software, which will be important if we want researchers to connect their specialised local tooling (e.g., for model training monitoring).

Our plans for year 2 include the development of a PoC by M18 to prove the technical feasibility of the architecture, further identification of requirements, as well as continuous engagement in discussions within the consortium, and most importantly, with our data providers, in order to improve our understanding of their requirements and to make necessary technical adjustments. We also plan to follow and align with other initiatives, data space projects, their standards and terminologies.

Specifically, we have already identified several concrete points of interest that will be prioritized in upcoming discussions:

- Design and development of UI components.
- Definition of additional user roles and detailed user stories to shape user experience and their engagement with the platform (as ML model trainers, external researchers, care providers, admins, etc.)

- Unified approach to auditing across the platform and standardization of the logs across all services, which would also enable requested features, such as transparency reporting.
- Platform and workflow monitoring, from both technical and user perspective, for obtaining information about service availability, processing status, request status, etc.
- Defining the responsibilities of the Algorithm Approval Committee and their engagement with the platform, including discussing the sustainability of the approach.
- Following the development of related initiatives like EHDS and TEHDAS in order to provide them with advice and feedback based on the experience we gain when developing IDERHA platform, as well as try to ensure alignment with the emerging standards.

Conclusion

We conclude that there is no deviation from the anticipated scope of this delivery. In this past year, the architecture has been frequently discussed in diverse contexts – legal, technical, functional – and our approach did address most needs with relatively minor adjustments. We anticipate further refinements of the architecture by M24, driven by the PoC in M18 and increasingly detailed requirement specifications through findings within the consortium.

Repository for primary data

- Not applicable

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